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IMPROVED CUCKOO SEARCH ALGORITHM FOR FEEDFORWARD NEURAL NETWORK TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

The cuckoo search algorithm is a recently developed meta-heuristic optimization algorithm, which is suitable for solving optimization problems. To enhance the accuracy and convergence rate of this algorithm, an improved cuckoo search algorithm is proposed in this paper. Normally, the parameters of the cuckoo search are kept constant. This may lead to decreasing the efficiency of the algorithm. To cope with this issue, a proper strategy for tuning the cuckoo search parameters is presented. Then, it is employed for training feedforward neural networks for two benchmark classification problems. Finally, the performance of the proposed algorithm is compared with that of the standard cuckoo search. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Classification, cuckoo search algorithm, feedforward neural network, optimization.

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